

AGRICULTURE IMPROVEMENT MEASURES

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ABSTRACT:

Increasing the economic efficiency of agriculture, first of all, serves to fulfill the requirements of the country's food strategy directions and ensure food safety. Also, on the other hand, this goal will be achieved through the rational use of the available labor, land, water, material and financial resources of the cotton-growing enterprises, regardless of the forms of ownership, on the basis of improving the economic relations between them.

The issue of development of cotton cultivation and increase of its economic efficiency has been studied by researchers and practitioners as a global economic problem. However, most of these researches were conducted in the conditions where the legal and economic independence of economic subjects was not ensured, and there were insufficient conditions for the materialization of scientific and practical proposals in this regard into the conditions of real economic management, or they were not due to the nature of the existing political system. it was not right. Now, based on the study of various views and concepts in the existing scientific literature, it has become necessary to advance new research, views and opinions that can be realized in the conditions of the market economy. Because any new economic-political system must have concepts that meet all the unique requirements for its survival and strengthening.

In recent years, the material and technical base of the cotton industry is not up to the level of demand, it is necessary to further improve the material

interests of the producers and the state support measures of the industry in accordance with the market requirements, and the use of new techniques and technologies in the production of the industry. Inadequate promotion of production, imperfect economic relations between producers and processors, and traders, and other similar issues have a negative impact on the sustainable development of cotton production. On January 28, 2022, the Decree No. PF-60 of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On the Development Strategy of the New Uzbekistan for 2022-2026" was signed and the new Development Strategy of Uzbekistan was adopted with this decree. In the 30th goal of the 3rd section of the strategy entitled "Rapid development of the national economy and ensuring high growth rates": The tasks "to increase the income of peasants and farmers by at least 2 times through the intensive development of agriculture on a scientific basis, to reach the annual growth of agriculture by at least 5%", and for the successful implementation of these tasks, the main part of the foreign currency income of the country is determined. It is important to develop and increase the economic efficiency of cotton growing.

Development of scientifically based and practical opinions, suggestions and recommendations on solving the above problems is one of the most urgent issues of today.

Based on the opinions and opinions of scientists who have conducted research on the methodology of economic efficiency evaluation until now, they can be conditionally divided into two groups. Scientists belonging to the first group believe that the criterion indicator of economic efficiency should be the only one.

The cotton complex occupies an important place in the process of socio-economic development, and it is of great importance for the economy of the country, which dominates its successful development. Cotton products processed in factories are very important raw materials for the light and food industry. Cotton products are also used in heavy industry. Up to 300 types of consumer products and technical products are made from cotton raw materials. In the economy of our country, the weight of cotton growing and cotton ginning industry is large. As the industry develops, other sectors of the national economy will also develop. From this point of view, further development of cotton growing is considered one of the priorities of our republic. It is known that our country has long been famous for its climate, serunum soil, underground and surface resources. The main factor for

achieving such success is the constant attention paid to the sector by our government, and especially economic benefits, scientific and technical achievements and the introduction of advanced technologies, opening a big way for the farming movement. Thanks to the gradual reforms, the material and technical base of farms is getting stronger year by year.

Economists of our country and foreign countries on the problems of improving the economic and legal mechanisms of the land area allocated for cotton in Agroclusters and increasing the efficiency of the use of land resources in the production of agricultural products, improving the organizational and economic mechanisms of the effective organization of the network and developing it on an innovative basis in the conditions of the market economy. who have conducted scientific and research work in various directions. The most important factor determining the economic efficiency of cotton cultivation is the yield. As a rule, the higher the yield, the lower the cost and labor costs per quintal of product, and, accordingly, the profitability will be higher. However, such a situation is observed when agriculture develops under normal conditions, that is, there is no disparity in the prices of material and technical resources and agricultural products, and the necessary support is provided to producers by the state. It is important to take into account the unique characteristics of the network in the development of cotton. These features establish some of the features that distinguish cotton farming from other industries. Including:

- that the development of cotton production is a priority in meeting the demand of industrial enterprises for raw materials and solving social problems;

- making raw materials grown in the cotton industry suitable for consumption by members of society requires several stages of processing;

- that cotton growers do not have the opportunity to satisfy their consumption requirements of a certain form with the intermediate finished product (producers of vegetables, grain, livestock products can use the finished product for personal consumption without any further processing);

- that the production of raw cotton is an industry that requires regular regulation by labor and economic means, etc.

- Increasing labor productivity is important for network development and economic efficiency. Labor productivity in cotton farming is the process of reducing the labor costs required to produce a unit of output and is based on:

- financial stability of cotton farms;
- the existence of an effective material-technical and services market;
- level of network mechanization;
- product production in accordance with demand and supply;
- less use of live labor, etc.

In the conditions where the laws of market relations apply, the main goal of cotton growers is to get more income, and they choose the most convenient and effective way to achieve their goals. Ultimately, the chosen path creates the formation of labor productivity in different ways. If there is cheap labor in the network, the level of their use will be high and will justify the tendency of labor productivity to decrease, and the cheapness of the services of technical means will justify the tendency of labor productivity to grow in the cotton industry. So, achieving labor productivity in cotton farming is the basis for the formation of the following positive aspects in the industry:

- reduction of labor costs, efficient use of land, water, and material resources;
- achieving an intensive increase in the volume of raw cotton;
- decrease in product cost and increase in income;
- increasing the material interests of cotton growers, etc.

The issue of supply of material and technical resources in cotton farming is considered to be one of the factors that have a strong impact on the development of the industry, and in the conditions of transition to market relations, their purchase prices are required to be proportional to the purchase prices of the raw materials being produced. On the contrary, the disparity between the prices of the material and technical resources produced in the industry and used in cotton production and the purchase price of cotton raw materials causes the price of cotton to rise, and this situation can have a serious negative impact on the economic efficiency of cotton production. However, the economic efficiency of cotton farming depends not only on the prices of material and technical means, but also on their effective use. Failure to carry out agrotechnical activities on time due to non-effective use of material and technical means causes a decrease in soil fertility and a decrease in cotton yield.

Social factors affecting network development are directly related to ownership relations. Adjustment of ownership and use of property in cotton farming to the requirements of market relations, in turn, leads to

improvement of the relations of cotton growers to property and labor. On this basis, it is necessary to improve the material benefit system in the formation of agrarian relations in cotton farming. This is the main requirement of the market economy based on social relations. The implementation of this goal will depend on the improvement of the legal and regulatory documents in force in the network. From this point of view, it is an objective necessity to determine the goals and tasks of the legal and regulatory documents adopted and applied in connection with the organization and development of cotton production based on the requirements of the market economy based on social relations.

In conclusion, it can be noted that the composition of the factors affecting the development of cotton production in Uzbekistan has changed based on the unique characteristics of each period, and their influence on the development of the sector is also different in each period. has been The common fact for all studied periods is that cotton growing was not only agriculture, but the leading branch of the country's economy. Of course, there are many factors to increase economic efficiency: among them, the level of technology used, the availability of modern techniques, the quality of seeds, the extent of use of mineral fertilizers and plant protection agents are important. rin takes over.

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